

STRESS LEVEL OF BAYBAY I DISTRICT TEACHERS

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Stress Level of Baybay I District Teachers

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ABSTRACT

This study utilized the descriptive survey method of research which aimed to determine the stress level of Baybay I District teachers. This study focused on five stress level indicators: physical, sleep, behavior, emotional, and personal habits. A total of 154 teachers who were 36-50 years old who belong middle age, females, married, with MA units, 13 years or more in service, and most of them were teaching grade six served as respondents. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics through frequency counting and percentages, t-test for the differences in means, analysis of variance (ANOVA), and computer software for data analysis used to aid statistical computations. Results of the study revealed that physical, emotional, and personal habits gave a high-stress level to the teachers while sleep and behavior gave a medium stress level to the teachers. Physical has a significant relationship in terms of age. A negative correlation means that there is an opposite relationship between age and level of stress. This implied that the more mature a teacher is, the more that they could be able to manage different situations. Age is significantly related to emotions since younger teachers were not showing so much emotion in terms of demands, unlike older teachers who were expressive if one cannot do the job one can ask for help from younger teachers. Personal habits have a significant relationship in terms of age since younger teachers experience higher stress. This shows that most of the young teachers were not able to spend time for family bonding because they were tired of preparing reports to be submitted. Behavior has a significant relationship to sexes since males have significantly higher mean points total than females, which means that male teachers have higher stress ratings compared to female teachers. As to their civil status, it has a significant relationship in terms of sleep. Appendix F reveals that married teachers have experienced a “medium stress level” while solo parents experienced a “danger stress level” and single, divorced/separated, and widowed have experienced a “high-stress level”.

Keywords: *stress indicators, stress level, stress management plan*

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INTRODUCTION

Job stress is the harmful physical and emotional responses that occur when the requirements of the job do not match the capabilities, resources, or needs of the worker. Too much stress among teachers might lead to the poor physical, mental, and emotional state of teachers and possibly affect teacher performance, teacher-student relationship, and/or consequently, student performance as well (Strategies for Preventing Job Stress, 2012). Role ambiguity, organizational change, job demands, bullying, and violence are some of the common stress factors happening in the workplace (European Company Survey, 2013). Moreover, economic crisis or downturn has supplemented an increase in suicidal cases and that has brought about a 0.79% rise in suicide cases of people under 65 of age for every 1% increase in unemployment and about 4.45% in deaths due to alcohol abuse (Workplace Stress: A Collective Challenge, 2016).

Stress affects the life of a teacher. A teacher is a kingpin in the entire system of education. The work of a teacher is physically, mentally, emotionally, and behaviorally challenging. A teacher needs to use a lot of energy in his daily chores in the classroom coupled with his personal and family commitments. This trend which is routine for a teacher forwards a lot of stress to the teacher (Kaur, 2011). A good amount of stress that can be handled by the teacher helps denote positive influences as well as alleviating the negative side of either arising or even stopping it (Mai and Vu, 2016). Teachers should create a healthy working environment, practicing a constructive preventive culture in the organization, increasing productivity that would eventually respond to greater economic growth and impact excellent teacher performance as a whole (Workplace Stress: A Collective Challenge, 2016).

The Department of Education has called on teachers to manage stress by maximizing the use of technology after an accident in Leyte province where a teacher committed suicide due to “paperwork”. The suicide incident is a wake-up call for public school teachers to learn how to manage work pressures (Philippine News Agency, 2018). In addition, a large share of 23 percent, of teachers experience stress because of their bosses or supervisors. One male reader answered “Poor management at work”. Others blamed it on job demands such as “deadlines” and being behind schedule, while some attributed it to their co-workers (Filipinos Top Causes of Stress Job Traffic Money, 2017).

It has been observed by the researcher that teachers in Baybay I District expressed that it was stressful on their part because of hectic schedules, work overload, and long hours to do their extra tasks rather than to facilitate learning with their pupils. They further said that teacher which is to give quality education is not realized due to other tasks which should be submitted as soon as possible. The preparation of the lesson and teaching time is spent on making reports, so pupils are given seatwork.

With this clamor of teachers, this study is thought of to investigate on stress level of Baybay I District teachers, Baybay City Division to propose a stress management plan and help teachers choose positive coping strategies. The result of this study will be helpful to school administrators to help teachers handle stress through the proposed stress management plan. The learners who are the recipients of the teacher’s work performance would benefit from less stressed teachers. More importantly, the teachers will be guided on how they will manage their stress.

Research Questions

This study determined the stress level of Baybay I District teachers, Baybay City Division with the end view of proposing a stress management plan. To clarify further the main problem, this study answered the following questions:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of Baybay I District teachers in terms of the following?
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Sex
 - 1.3 Civil status
 - 1.4 Educational Attainment
 - 1.5 length of service
 - 1.6 Grade Assignment
2. What is the stress level of Baybay I District teachers in terms of the following?
 - 2.1 Physical Indicators
 - 2.2 Sleep Indicators
 - 2.3 Behavior Indicators
 - 2.4 Emotional Indicators
 - 2.5 Personal habits Indicators
3. Is there a significant relationship among socio-demographic profile, stress indicators, and stress level of teachers?
4. What stress management plan can be designed for teachers from the results of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study utilized the descriptive method to determine the stress level of Baybay I District teachers in terms of physical indicators, sleep indicators, behavior indicators, emotional indicators, and personal habits. Such a method was employed because it involved description, recording, analysis, and interpretations of existing conditions of the stress level of teachers with the questionnaire as a tool for data gathering.

The Sample and Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in Baybay I District, Baybay City Division, Baybay City, Leyte, academic year 2018-2019. Baybay I District is composed of 13 monograde classes. The respondents of the study were all regular-permanent teachers of public elementary schools, as shown in Table 1, there were 138 females and 16 males involved in the study. Hence, a total of 154 teachers served as respondents.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents

Name of School	Number of Teachers		Total
	Female	Male	
Baybay I Central	51	8	59
Buenavista	6	1	7
Candadam	8	1	9
Gaas	8	0	8
Gacat	9	0	9
Hibunawan	7	0	7
Imelda	6	0	6
Kambonggan	5	1	6
Kansungka	5	2	7
Kilim	12	1	13
Mailhi	6	2	8
San Isidro	7	0	7
Sta. Cruz	8	0	8
Total	138	16	154

Research Instrument

The study aimed to investigate the stress level of Baybay I District teachers through the stress indicators questionnaire which was adopted by the counseling team international. The questionnaire is divided into two parts. The first part is on the socio-demographic profile of Baybay I District teachers specifically about age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, length of service, and grade assignment. The second part of the instrument explored the stress level of Baybay I District teachers. The stress level of teachers is categorized into five stress indicators namely, physical indicators, sleep indicators, behavior indicators, emotional indicators, and personal habit indicators. A five-point scale was used to evaluate the level of stress of the teachers where 1 is very low if the stress indicators were never experienced, 2 is medium if the stress indicators were almost never experienced, 3 is high if the stress indicators were some of the times experienced, 4 is very high if the stress indicators were most of the time experienced and 5 is danger if the stress indicators were almost always experienced.

Data Gathering

The researcher sought permission and endorsement from the School's Division Superintendent of Baybay City Division. After getting the superintendent's approval, the researcher sent a letter to the different school principals and heads of the target schools. Administration of the questionnaires was done personally to facilitate data gathering and retrieval.

The socio-demographic profile which includes age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, length of service, and grade assignment was analyzed using descriptive statistics through frequency counting and percentages by using the formula:

$$P = f/N \times 100$$

Where: P = percentage

f = frequency

N = total number of respondents

The following levels of categorization was employed:

Age

<u>Range</u>	<u>Description</u>
20 – 35 years old	Young
36 – 50 years old	Middle Age
51 – 65 years old	Old

Sex

Description

Male
Female

Civil Status

Description

Single	Widowed
Married	Solo parent
Divorced/Separated	

Educational Attainment

Description

M.A Units	Ed. D. / Ph. D. Units
M.A CAR	Ed. D. / Ph. D. CAR
M.A Graduate	Ed. D. / Ph. D. Graduate

Length of Service

<u>Range</u>	<u>Description</u>
1 – 3 years	Novice
4 – 12 years	Experienced
13 years or more	Highly Experienced

Grade Assignment

Description

Kindergarten	Grade Four
Grade One	Grade Five
Grade Two	Grade Six
Grade Three	

The stress level is categorized into:

- Very low – The stress indicators were never experienced.
- Medium – The stress indicators were almost never experienced.
- High - The stress indicators were some of the times experienced.
- Very high - The stress indicators were most of the time experienced.
- Danger - The stress indicators were almost always experienced.

To measure the personal stress level, the following was used:

<u>Stress Level Indicators</u>	<u>Stress Level</u>				
	Very Low	Medium	High	Very High	Danger
A. Physical Indicators - Point Total	22	30	38	48	54+
B. Sleep Indicators Point Total	5.....	8.....	10.....	12.....	14+
C. Behavior Indicators Point Total	18	27.....	36.....	45.....	50+
D. Emotional Indicators Point Total	21.....	29.....	37.....	46.....	55+
E. Personal Habits Point Total	9.....	15.....	20.....	25.....	30+

To describe the personal stress level per indicator, the following was used:

<u>Stress Level Indicators</u>	<u>Stress Level</u>				
	Very Low	Medium	High	Very High	Danger
A. Physical Indicators - Point Total	161	220	279	352	396+
B. Sleep Indicators Point Total	154.....	246.....	308.....	370.....	431+
C. Behavior Indicators Point Total	163	245.....	326.....	408.....	452+
D. Emotional Indicators Point Total	154.....	213.....	271.....	337.....	403+
E. Personal Habits Point Total	154.....	257.....	342.....	428.....	513+

In pointing out the significant relationship between the socio-demographic profile, stress indicators, and stress level of Baybay I District teachers, t-tests for the differences in means and analysis of variance (ANOVA) were used.

$$t = \frac{\bar{X}_1 - \bar{X}_2}{\sqrt{SE_1^2 + SE_2^2}}$$

$$\text{Where: } SE_1 = \frac{Sd_1}{\sqrt{N}} \quad \text{and} \quad SE_2 = \frac{Sd_2}{\sqrt{N}}$$

X_1 – mean of the first group

X_2 – mean of the second group

Sd_1 – Standard deviation of the first group

Sd_2 – Standard deviation of the second group

SE_1 – Standard error of the first group

SE_2 – Standard error of the second group

Computer software for data analysis was used to aid statistical computations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the organized data and information in answer to the objectives of the study. It shows the socio-demographic profile of Baybay I District teachers such as age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, length of service and grade assignment, the stress level of Baybay I District teachers in terms of physical indicators, sleep indicators, behavior indicators, emotional indicators and personal habits, the significant relationship among socio-demographic profile, stress indicators and stress level of teachers. Lastly, a proposed stress management plan from the results of the study.

Socio-Demographic Profile of Baybay I District Teachers

The socio-demographic profile of Baybay I District teachers includes the following variables: age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, length of service, and grade assignment. Data on socio-demographic profiles is reflected in Table 2.

Table 2. Socio-Demographic Profile of Baybay I District Teachers

Socio-Demographic Profile	Frequency	Percentage
A. Age		
20-35 years old	35	23%
36-50 years old	84	55%
51-65 years old	35	23%
Total	154	100%
B. Sex		
Male	16	10%
Female	138	90%
Total	154	100%
C. Civil Status		
Single	23	15%
Married	121	79%
Divorced/Separated	2	1%
Widowed	7	5%
Solo Parent	1	1%
Total	154	100%
D. Educational Attainment		
MA Units	81	53%
MA CAR	58	38%
MA Graduate	12	8%
Ed.D. /Ph.D. Units	2	1%
		1%
		0%
Total	154	100%
E. Length of Service		
1-3 years	16	10%
4-12 years	58	38%
13 years or more	80	52%
Total	154	100%
F. Grade Assignment		
Kindergarten	18	12%
Grade One	21	14%
Grade Two	17	11%
Grade Three	21	14%
Grade Four	18	12%
Grade Five	25	16%
Grade Six	29	19%
SPED	5	3%
Total	154	100%

Table 2 continued. Socio-Demographic Profile of Baybay I

Age. Age is a variable in the study which is categorized into three brackets. Results revealed that there were 55% or 84 out of 154 teachers whose ages ranged from 36-50 years old, 23% or 35 were 51-65 years old, and only 23% or 35 out of 154 teachers were 20-35 years old. This indicates that most of the teachers serving in Baybay I District are in the middle age in which teachers are more experienced in the field of teaching.

Sex. This variable refers to male and female respondents. Data revealed that 90% or 138 out of 154 respondents were females and 10% or 16 out of 154 respondents were males. It shows that most of the teachers serving in Baybay I District are female teachers.

Civil Status. Civil status is a variable in the study which was categorized into five, namely: single, married, divorced/separated, widowed, and solo parent. The data shows that 79% or 121 out of 154 respondents were married teachers which could mean that most of the teachers have great responsibilities in their personal life. Being married is challenging and carries different responsibilities. Anbu (2015) states that married teachers are shouldering more responsibility than the unmarried in terms of school work as well as in the family and society, hence they are in the position to satisfy all the dimensions.

Educational Attainment. The data shows that 53% or 81 out of 154 respondents in Baybay I District have attained MA units. This shows that the respondents have tried to improve themselves professionally.

Length of Service. Length of service refers to how long the teacher is teaching. Results revealed that there were 52% or 80 out of 154 respondents whose teaching experience was 13 years or more and only 10% or 16 out of 154 respondents whose teaching experience was 1-3 years. This means that most of the teachers serving in Baybay I District are highly experienced in the field of teaching.

Grade Assignment. Each grade was represented in the study. Among the grade assignments, the data revealed that 19% or 29 out of 154 respondents in Baybay I District were teaching grade six. This is due to the fact that more teachers in Grade six are Special Subject Teachers which means that they do not handle advisory classes. For SPED or Special Education teachers only 3% or 5 out of 154 teachers were teaching because only Baybay I Central School is offering SPED classes in Baybay I District.

Stress Level of Baybay I District Teachers

The stress level is categorized into the following variables: physical indicators, sleep indicators, behavior indicators, emotional indicators, and personal habits. Table 3 presents the results of the study.

Table 3. Distribution of Stress Level on Physical Indicators

Physical Indicators	Point Total	Description
1. My body feels tense all over.	412	Danger
2. I have a nervous sweat or sweaty palms.	305	High
3. I have a hard time feeling really relaxed.	416	Danger
4. I have severe or chronic lower back pain.	383	Very High
5. I get severe or chronic headaches.	378	Very High
6. I get tension or muscle spasms in my face, jaw, neck, or shoulders.	355	Very High

7. My stomach quivers or feels upset. High	373	Very
8. I get skin rashes or itching.	285	High
9. I have problems with my bowels (constipation, diarrhea).	330	High
10. I need to urinate more than most people. High	358	Very
11. My ulcer bothers me.	253	High
12. I feel short of breath after mild exercise like climbing up four flights of stairs.	409	Danger
13. Compared to most people, I have a very small or a large appetite.	414	Danger
14. My weight is more than 15 pounds higher than what is High recommended for a person my height and build.	395	Very
15. I smoke tobacco/cigarette. Low	170	Very
16. I get sharp chest pains when I'm physically active.	284	High
17. I lack physical energy. High	387	Very
18. When I'm resting, my heart beats more than 100 times a minute.	295	High
19. Because of my busy schedule I miss at least two meals during Medium the week.	270	
20. I don't really plan my meals for balanced nutrition. Danger	408	
21. I spend less than 3 hours a week getting vigorous physical exercise (running, playing basketball, tennis, swimming, etc).	348	High
Total	7228	
Point Total	344	HIGH

Physical Indicators. Data in Table 3 reveals a “High Stress Level” which means that the stress indicators were some of the time experienced by the respondents. This result is attributed to the fact that from the twenty-one indicators, five were claimed as “Danger Stress Level”, seven were expressed as “Very High-Stress Level”, seven as “High”, one for “Medium Stress Level”, and one for “Very Low-Stress Level”. Among the indicators described as Danger Stress Level, it is manifested that the respondents expressed having a hard time feeling relaxed. Relaxation is vital to one’s health. Relaxation techniques are a great way to help with stress management. Relaxation is not only about peace of mind or enjoying a hobby. Relaxation is a process that decreases the effects of stress on the mind and body (Relaxation Techniques: Try These Steps to Reduce Stress, 2017). The respondents expounded that compared to most people, they have a very small or a large appetite. Losing of appetite is a sign of job stress. Sissons (2018) supports that anyone experiences loss of appetite for many different reasons and other people tend to eat less or lose interest in food when they undergo stress.

The respondents pointed out that their bodies felt tense all over and felt short of breath after mild exercise like climbing up four flights of stairs. Breathing is one way to release the stress from work. Breathing exercises offer an extremely simple, effective, and convenient way to relieve stress reverse stress response, and reduce the negative effects of stress (Scott, 2019). The respondents expressed that they don’t really plan meals for balanced nutrition. Planning meals for balanced nutrition helps activate and energize in facing the demands. This statement

is supported by the National Heart Lung and Blood Institute (2015) which points out that a healthy eating plan provides the body with nutrients. Most significantly, it will lower the risk of heart disease and other health conditions. With these findings, teachers need to learn how to relax despite their hectic schedules and unleash stress by taking deep breaths, doing short exercises, enough hours of sleep, and being able to eat nutritious food.

Table 3.1 Distribution of Stress Level on Sleep Indicators

Sleep Indicators	Point Total	Description
1. I have trouble falling asleep.	389	Very High
2. I take pills to get to sleep.	162	Very Low
3. I have nightmares or repeated bad dreams.	260	Medium
4. I wake up at least once in the middle of the night for no apparent reason.	351	High
5. No matter how much sleep I get, I wake feeling tired.	363	High
Total	1525	
Point Total	305	MEDIUM

Sleep Indicators. Sleep is one of the variables in determining stress levels. Five indicators were utilized to measure this. Data presented in Table 3.1 shows a point total of 305 which is described as “Medium Stress Level” which means that these indicators were almost never experienced by the respondents. However, looking closely at the point total of 305 this is very close to the 308-point total which is a “High Stress Level”. Based on Table 3.1, from the five indicators, one was claimed as a “Very High-Stress Level” which is most of the time experienced by the respondents, and one a “Very Low-Stress Level” which is never experienced by the respondents.

Respondents expressed that they experienced trouble falling asleep because they brought paperwork at home, worked late at night, worried a lot if they could not finish the tasks on time, and had difficulty feeling relaxed with unfinished tasks. Apparently, enough hours of sleep can help in revitalizing one’s body. Johnson (2018) states that stress often impacts sleep quality and duration. Stress and lack of sleep can both have a severe impact on physical and mental health. Experts recommend that people aim for 7-9 hours of sleep at night, depending on their age and other factors. Not getting hours of sleep can cause a negative mood, low energy, difficulty concentrating, and a general inability to function as usual.

Table 3.2 Distribution of Stress Level on Behavior Indicators

Behavioral Indicators	Point Total	Description
1. I stutter or get tongue-tied when I talk to other people.	356	High
2. I try to work while I'm eating lunch.	358	High
3. I have to work late.	413	Very High
4. I go to work even when I feel sick.	464	Danger
5. I have to bring work home.	555	Danger
6. I drink alcohol or use drugs to relax.	198	Very Low
7. I have more than two beers, eight ounces of wine or three ounces of hard liquor a day.	174	Very Low
8. When I drink, I like to get really drunk.	173	Very Low

9. I get drunk or "high" with other drugs more than once a week. Low	163	Very
10. When I'm feeling high from alcohol or drugs I will drive a Low motor vehicle.	164	Very
11. I tend to stumble when walking, or have more accidents than Low other people.	190	Very
12. In any given week, I take at least one prescription drug without Low the recommendation of a physician, e.g. amphetamines, barbiturates.	196	Very
13. I have problems with my sex life.	194	Very Low
14. At least once during the week I will make bets for money.	238	Very Low
15. After dinner I spend more time alone or watching TV than I do talking with my family or friends.	353	High
16. I arrive at work late.	317	Medium
17. At least once during the week I have a shouting match with a co-worker or supervisor.	174	Very Low
Total	4680	
Point Total	275	MEDIUM

Behavior Indicators. In measuring this variable, seventeen indicators were used. Two were claimed as a “Danger Stress Level”, one for “Very High-Stress Level”, three were described as having a “High-Stress Level”, one for “Medium” and ten were expressed as “Very Low-Stress Level. One of the indicators interpreted as “Danger Stress Level” expressed by the respondents was that they brought their work at home with a point total of 555. Furthermore, they stressed that they brought paper works at home even on weekends which affected spending time for family bonding.

It shows also that they go to work even if they feel sick with a point total of 464 which is interpreted as “Danger”. Turna (2014) supports that if the teacher is in a stressful environment, his/her efficiency and effectiveness towards teaching might decrease and this might be reflected upon the student and even the whole society negatively.

The result revealed on behavior indicators gave a general point total of 275 which is described as a “Medium Stress Level”. This means that the stress indicators were almost never experienced by the respondents. These findings entail that teachers don’t need to bring paperwork at home even on weekends which could affect spending time for family bonding. Furthermore, teachers should not go to work if feeling sick, learn to relax despite their busy schedules, avoid eating while working, and work late at night instead of going to bed early to get sufficient hours of sleep.

Table 3.3 Distribution of Stress Level on Emotional Indicators

Emotional Indicators	Point Total	Description
1. I have found the best way to deal with hassles and to deal with hassles and problems is to consciously avoid thinking or talking about them.	432	Danger
2. I have trouble remembering things.	412	Danger

3. I feel anxious or frightened about problems I can't really describe.	367	Very High
4. I worry a lot.	392	Very High
5. It is important for me not to show my emotions to my family.	423	Danger
6. It is hard for me to relax at home.	328	High
7. It's best if I don't tell even my closest friend how I'm really feeling.	376	Very High
8. I find it hard to talk when I get excited.	322	High
9. I feel very angry inside.	328	High
10. I have temper outbursts I can't control.	317	High
11. When people criticize me, even in friendly, constructive way, I feel offended.	343	Very High
12. I feel extremely sensitive and irritable.	351	Very High
13. My emotions change unpredictably and without any apparent reason.	319	High
14. I feel like I really can't trust anyone.	343	Very High
15. I feel like other people don't understand me.	314	High
16. I really don't feel good about myself.	286	High
17. Generally I am not optimistic about my future.	319	High
18. I feel very tired and disinterested in life.	252	Medium
19. Impulsive behavior has caused me problems.	300	High
20. I have felt so bad that I thought of hurting myself.	230	Medium
21. When I have an important personal problem I can't solve myself, I do not seek professional help.	300	High
Total	7054	
Point Total	335	HIGH

Emotional Indicators. Emotion is one of the indicators in determining the stress level of the teachers. Data displayed in Table 3.3 presents a general point total of 335 which is described as “High Stress Level” meaning that these indicators were some of the time experienced by the respondents. However, as seen closely at the point total of 335 this is very close to 337 point total which is “Very High Stress Level”. In measuring this variable, twenty-one indicators were utilized. Results revealed that three were expressed as “Danger Stress Level”.

Among the dangers, respondents revealed that they consciously avoid thinking or talking about problems. Being conscious of hassles and problems may create stress and it may affect the teacher's quality performance. Furthermore, they stressed that it is important for them not to show their emotions to their family. What is Emotional Stress Can Affect Your Spine Overall Health (2018) states that emotional stress can manifest in different ways including anxiety, depression, and hostility. On the other hand, respondents have trouble remembering things. If a person is forgetful, he/she cannot perform well in his/her task because of the many responsibilities assigned to him/her.

These findings require that teachers need to be open-minded about problems they have encountered and be able to express emotions to family and co-workers so that everyone can

help as much as possible, learn to relax, and stay calm whatever tasks are given. Teachers should not worry if the tasks are not done on time and learn to control their temper despite of hectic schedules.

Table 3.4 Distribution of Stress Levels on Personal Habits

Personal Habits	Point Total	Description
1. I spend less than three hours a week working on a hobby of mine.	397	High
2. I spend less than one hour a week writing personal letters, writing in a diary or writing creatively.	309	Medium
3. I spend less than 30 minutes a week talking casually with my neighbors.	381	High
4. I lack time to read the daily newspaper.	436	Very High
5. I watch television for entertainment more than one hour a day.	499	Very High
6. I drive in a motor vehicle faster than the speed limit for the excitement and challenge of it.	220	Very Low
7. I spend less than 30 minutes a day working toward a life goal or ambition of mine.	429	Very High
8. My day to day living is not really affected by my religious beliefs or my philosophy of life.	457	Very High
9. When I feel stressed, it is difficult for me to plan time and activities to constructively release my stress.	425	High
Total	3553	
Point Total	394	HIGH

Personal Habits. Personal habits are composed of nine indicators in determining the stress level of the respondents. Through the data presented in Table 3.4, four were expressed as “Very High-Stress Level”, three for “High-Stress Level”, one for “Medium” and one for “Very Low-Stress Level”. It was evident that the respondents were watching television for entertainment more than one hour a day, lacked time to read the daily newspaper, day-to-day living was not affected by religious beliefs or philosophy of life, and spent less than 30 minutes a day working toward a life goal or ambition.

Results revealed on personal habits expressed as “High Stress Level” which means that these indicators were some of the times experienced by the respondents with a general point total of 394. It shows also that teachers were affected by these indicators and there’s a need to activate their habits to have a better and more meaningful life. These outcomes imply that teachers need to intensify and perform personal habits to unleash stress by balancing one’s time for leisure, family, and work. Vespi (2019) states that successful people have a routine of daily or weekly habits that reinforce the things that are most important to them. By practicing a set of personal success habits, maintaining a positive outlook, keeping focused on their priorities, and having more energy, and a greater sense of satisfaction with life.

Table 3.5 Summary of Stress Level of Baybay I District Teachers

Stress Indicators	Stress Level
Physical	High
Sleep	Medium
Behavior	Medium
Emotional	High
Personal Habits	High

Relationship between Socio-Demographic Profile, Stress Indicators and Stress Level of Teachers

In pointing out the significant relationship of the socio-demographic profile, stress indicators and stress level of Baybay I District teachers, t-test for the differences in means, analysis of variance (ANOVA) and computer software for data analysis were used to aid statistical computations.

Table 4.1 Correlation between Age and Level of Stress

Stress Indicators	N	Correlation Coefficient (r)	Relationship	p-value (2-tailed)	Description
Physical	154	-0.164	Low Negative	0.042	Significant
Sleep	154	-0.054	Negligible	0.508	Not Significant
Behavior	154	-0.150	Low Negative	0.063	Not Significant
Emotional	154	-0.166	Low Negative	0.039	Significant
Personal Habits	154	-0.159	Low Negative	0.049	Significant

Correlation between Age and Level of Stress

Table 4.1 presents the correlation between the age profile and stress level of teachers. Results revealed that age is significantly related to physical, emotional, and personal habits and stress levels. A negative correlation means that there is an opposite relationship between age and level of stress. This implied that the more mature a teacher is, the more that they could be able to manage different situations. De Nobile and McCormick (2011) state that younger staff experience a higher level of stress than older colleagues. It was evident that younger teachers experienced more physical stress than older teachers because younger teachers were still in a period of adjustment in terms of environment and workload.

However, Mmaduakonam and Orizu (2014) indicate that both older teachers and younger teachers exhibit a significantly higher level of stress than middle-aged teachers. This might be attributed to the fact that at middle age most teachers are trying to stabilize. The younger teachers probably exhibit higher levels of stress because they are yet struggling for survival. On the other hand, older teachers exhibit higher levels of stress probably because they have reached the peak of their careers.

Based on the same table, emotional indicators are significantly related to age profile of the Baybay I District teachers. It shows that younger teachers were not showing so much emotion

in terms of work demands, unlike older teachers who were expressive if one cannot do the job one can ask for help from the younger teachers. De Nobile and McCormick (2011) point out that younger teachers reported more incidents of burnout predominantly in terms of emotional exhaustion compared to older teachers. Kaur (2011) defines occupational stress as the physical and emotional response that occurs when a worker perceives an imbalance between the work demands and his/her capability and/or resources to meet these demands.

Personal habits are also significantly related to the age profile of the Baybay I District teachers. Younger teachers experienced higher stress. This shows that most of the young teachers were not able to spend time for family bonding because they were tired of preparing reports to be submitted. Vespi (2019) states that by practicing personal success habits, one should maintain a positive outlook, keep focused on priorities, and have more energy and a greater sense of satisfaction with life. Data displayed that age is not significantly related to sleep and behavior. The relationship for sleeping was negligible and behavior was low negative stress. This implied that age does not affect the level of stress in terms of sleep and behavior.

Table 4.2 Difference of Stress Levels between Sexes

Stress Indicator	Sex	N	Mean Point Total	Stress Level	t-Computed	p-value (2-tailed)	Description
Physical Significant	Male	16	49.63	Very High	0.861	0.401	Not Significant
	Female	138	46.62	High			
Sleep Significant	Male	16	10.56	High	0.723	0.479	Not Significant
	Female	138	9.83	Medium			
Behavior	Male	16	35.02	Medium	2.680	0.016	Significant
	Female	138	29.85	Medium			
Emotional Significant	Male	16	47.56	Very High	0.645	0.520	Not Significant
	Female	138	45.60	Very High			
Personal Habits Significant	Male	16	24.56	High	1.167	0.245	Not Significant
	Female	138	22.90	High			

Difference of Stress Levels between Sexes

In terms of the stress level between sexes, behavioral indicators show a significant relationship. As shown in Table 4.2 the male has a significantly higher mean point total than females, which means that male teachers have higher stress ratings compared to female teachers. These findings support the contention of Mondal et al. (2011) who state that there is a significant difference between male and female teachers, with male teachers having more psychological and physical stress than female teachers. Also, male teachers were reported to be more insecure and more concerned about financial matters, while females looked into the intrinsic facets of their jobs.

On the other hand, Bhadoria and Singh (2010) reported that female teachers tended to grumble more in tension than male teachers. Klasen (2010) supported the idea of variations between genders when his research showed female teachers faced greater workload stress and greater classroom stress from student behaviors. Female teachers averaged 13% more workload stress and 8% more classroom stress than male teachers. But both have experienced the same stress level which is a medium level of stress. It means that both male and female teachers can handle behavioral stress in whatever tasks and responsibilities are given by their superiors.

However, it is important not to neglect the medium level of stress because there are instances that this level of stress can still affect the performance of a teacher. On the other hand, when sexes were grouped according to physical, sleep, emotional, and personal habits the data revealed that there was no significant relationship. It means that these stress indicators were not affected with the sex of a teacher whether male or female.

Table 4.3 Difference of Stress Levels among Different Civil Status

Stress Indicator		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-Computed	Sig.	Description
Physical Significant	Between Groups	782.225	4	195.556	1.841	0.124	Not
	Within Groups	15831.125	149	106.249			
	Total	16613.351	153				
Sleep	Between Groups	98.766	4	24.692	2.815	0.027	Significant
	Within Groups	1306.773	149	8.770			
	Total	1405.539	153				
Behavior Significant	Between Groups	149.790	4	37.448	1.053	0.382	Not
	Within Groups	5300.833	149	35.576			
	Total	5450.623	153				
Emotional Significant	Between Groups	748.584	4	187.146	1.433	0.226	Not
	Within Groups	19457.572	149	130.588			
	Total	20206.156	153				
Personal Habits	Between Groups	363.108	4	90.777	3.292	0.013	Significant
	Within Groups	4109.106	149	27.578			
	Total	4472.214	153				

Difference of Stress Levels among Different Civil Status

Table 4.3 shows the differences in stress levels among different civil statuses. Results revealed that civil status is significantly related to sleep and personal habits. As shown in appendix F stress levels in terms of sleep and civil status differ. Married teachers have experienced a “medium stress level” while solo parents experienced a “danger stress level” and single, divorced/separated, and widowed have a “high stress level”.

On the other hand, it shows in appendix F that stress level in terms of personal habits and civil status also differs. Married teachers and widowed have a “high-stress level” while solo parents experience a “danger stress level”, single parents have a “very high stress level” and divorced/separated have a “medium stress level”. Popoola and Ilugbo (2010) point out that there is a significant positive relationship between marital status and level of job stress. This finding, however, contradicted that of Bloom et. al. (2007) as cited by David (2016) indicating there is no significant relationship between marital status and daily stress level. However, Anbu (2015) states that married teachers shoulder more responsibility than unmarried teachers in terms of school work as well as in the family and society, hence they are in the position to satisfy all the dimensions.

Based on the same table, it shows that the civil status of the Baybay I District teachers were not significantly related when grouped according to physical, behavioral, and emotional which could entail that married, divorced/separated, single, widowed, and solo parent experienced this stress.

Table 4.4 Difference of Stress Levels among Different Educational Attainment

Stress Indicator		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-Computed	Sig.	Description
Physical	Between Groups	828.039	4	207.010	1.954	0.104	Not Significant
	Within Groups	15785.312	149	105.942			
	Total	16613.351	153				
Sleep	Between Groups	97.796	4	24.449	2.786	0.029	Significant
	Within Groups	1307.743	149	8.777			
	Total	1405.539	153				
Behavior	Between Groups	149.588	4	37.397	1.051	0.383	Not Significant
	Within Groups	5301.035	149	35.577			
	Total	5450.623	153				
Emotional	Between Groups	201.843	4	50.461	0.376	0.826	Not Significant
	Within Groups	20004.313	149	134.257			
	Total	20206.156	153				

Personal Habits	Between Groups	60.466	4	15.117	0.511	0.728	Not
	Within Groups	4411.748	149	29.609			
	Total	4472.214	153				

Difference of Stress Levels among Different Educational Attainment

Table 4.4 shows that sleep indicators have a significant relationship to educational attainment. Appendix G reveals that for Doctor of Education/Doctor of Philosophy with Completed Academic Requirement, teachers experienced “very high sleep stress”, Master of Arts with Completed Academic Requirements experienced “high sleep stress”, Master of Arts with units and Master of Arts Graduate experienced “medium sleep stress”, while Doctor of Education /Doctor of Philosophy with units was in a “very low sleep stress”.

Moreover, Doctor of Education /Doctor of Philosophy with Completed Academic Requirements revealed “very high sleep stress” because taking the comprehensive exam for the doctoral degree is not easy for it still requires time to study, and spending sleepless nights is anticipated to get better results. The same goes with the master’s degree to pass the examination, which compels a student to study and work religiously before enrolling in thesis writing. On the other hand, looking for a Master’s degree and Doctor of Education/Doctor of Philosophy with units require students to comply with the course demands like take-home assignments, modules, attendance, and participation in class discussions which were preparatory before taking the comprehensive examination and dissertation hence, the sleep stress level is medium to low. This further connotes that students have better sleeping patterns compared to those students who have completed academic requirements and preparing for their comprehensive examination and dissertation.

Education is essential to one’s life. Aftab and Khatoon (2012) revealed that trained graduate teachers experienced higher occupational stress than post-graduate teachers. Teachers who have attained a lower level of qualification or were not trained enough would be more susceptible to malicious demands from others on the understanding that they are not confident enough to stand on their stance and belief, which further escalates their perception of their stressors. However, those teachers who have higher qualifications in education possess a deep knowledge of their subject.

Based on the table presented there was no significant relationship between the educational attainment of the Baybay I District teachers when grouped according to physical, behavior, emotional, and personal habits it is because both male and female teachers can manage stress in terms of physical, behavioral, emotional and personal habits in taking master’s degree or doctoral degree.

Table 4.5 Difference of Stress Levels among Different Length of Service

Stress Indicator	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-Computed	Sig.	Description
Physical Habits	323.525	2	161.762	1.499	0.227	Not

	Within Groups Total	16289.826	151	107.880			
		16613.351	153				
Sleep Significant	Between Groups	15.970	2	7.985	0.868	0.422	Not
	Within Groups Total	1389.569	151	9.202			
		1405.539	153				
Behavior Significant	Between Groups	79.444	2	39.722	1.117	0.330	Not
	Within Groups Total	5371.179	151	35.571			
		5450.623	153				
Emotional Significant	Between Groups	382.231	2	191.115	1.456	0.236	Not
	Within Groups Total	19823.925	151	131.284			
		20206.156	153				
Personal Significant Habits	Between Groups	48.294	2	24.147	0.824	0.441	Not
	Within Groups Total	4423.920	151	29.297			
		4472.214	153				

Difference of Stress Levels among Different Length of Service

Table 4.5 shows the differences between the stress level and the length of service. This shows that there is no significant relationship between the length of service of the Baybay I District teachers when grouped according to physical, sleep, behavior, emotional, and personal habits. These could entail that whether he or she has teaching experience from 1-3 years, 4-12 years, and 13 years or more the result showed that stress level would be the same in terms of the five stress level indicators. A highly experienced teacher is confident in teaching and dealing with pupils. Jahan and Sharma (2017) state that teachers having less teaching experience had higher levels of occupational stress than more experienced teachers because they may not be confident enough in teaching or dealing with disruptive pupils, due to less experience in their profession in comparison to their senior colleagues who are more confident in teaching and handling disruptive pupils. Experienced teachers can also manage different situations both in the classroom and in other related tasks.

Table 4.6 Difference of Stress Levels among Different Grade Assignment

Stress Indicator	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-Computed	Sig.	Description
Physical Significant	331.368	7	47.338	0.424	0.886	Not
Between Groups						

	Within Groups Total	16281.982	146	111.520			
Sleep Significant	Between Groups	28.460	7	4.066	0.431	0.882	Not
	Within Groups Total	1377.079	146	9.432			
Behavior Significant	Between Groups	233.801	7	33.400	0.935	0.482	Not
	Within Groups Total	5216.822	146	35.732			
Emotional Significant	Between Groups	855.213	7	122.173	0.922	0.492	Not
	Within Groups Total	19350.943	146	132.541			
Personal Significant Habits	Between Groups	121.826	7	17.404	0.584	0.768	Not
	Within Groups Total	4350.389	146	29.797			
	Groups Total	4472.214	153				

Difference of Stress Levels among Different Grade Assignment

Table 4.6 shows the differences between the stress level and the grade assignment. This shows that there is no significant relationship between the grade assignment of the Baybay I District teachers when grouped according to physical, sleep, behavior, emotional, and personal habits because each one has a different stress level in managing the class for each grade level and it was evident that they were not affected.

From the findings and results of the study, a proposed stress management plan was designed to help teachers in managing their stress. The stress management plan is a set of techniques and programs based from the result of the study specifically to those who experienced danger stress level, very high stress level and high stress level per indicator. It includes the rationale and the activities of each stress indicators. Each activity has personal commitment that will help and guide teachers in doing the plan. A designed management plan is attached as Appendix J.

CONCLUSION

Summary of Findings

The socio-demographic profile of Baybay I District teachers comprising 36-50 years old who belong to middle age, females, married, with MA units, 13 years or more in service, and most

of them were teaching grade six. The stress level of Baybay I District teachers diverge in different indicators like physical, emotional, and personal habits gave a high stress level while sleep and behavior gave a medium stress level.

There was a significant relationship in terms of age when grouped according to stress indicators namely physical, emotional, and personal habits. When it comes to behavior it has a significant relationship to sexes; as to their civil status, it has a significant relationship when grouped according to sleep and personal habits. Sleep indicators have a significant relationship among different educational attainment. In terms of length of service, there was no significant relationship when grouped according to physical, sleep, behavior, emotional, and personal habits. Concerning the grade assignment, there was no significant relationship when grouped according to physical, sleep, behavioral, emotional, and personal habits.

Conclusion

On the basis of the above findings, it is concluded that the socio-demographic profile of the Baybay I District teachers manifest a diverse teaching work force and do not relate to stress levels. Teachers took for granted their physical condition and bodily needs like relaxing, eating a balanced meal and doing exercises. Teachers' behavior demonstrated work driven attitude for working even when sick, brought home their work and work late at night. Emotionally, they avoid facing issues to refrain from conflicts. These manifestations contributed to stress level.

Recommendations

From the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Conduct trainings on stress and mental health.
2. Adopt the stress management plan in their monthly activities to cope positively with stress.
3. Assign stress management plan coordinator to oversee the implementation of the plans.
4. Encourage other researchers to conduct further studies in other districts of Baybay or in farther places to further test the validity of the study.

REFERENCES

- Aftab, M., and Khatoon, T. (2012). Demographic Differences and Occupational Stress of Secondary School Teachers. *European Journal of Scientific Research*. March Edition Vol. 8, No.5.
- Anbu, A. (2015). Professional Stress of Higher Secondary School Teachers. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development* 2(1):1-3.

- Bhadoria, D., and Singh, T. (2010). Relationships of Age and Gender with Burnout among Primary School Teachers. *Indian Journal of Social Science Researches*, Vol. 7(2), 1017. Retrieved from: <http://eujournal.org/files/journals/1/articles/90/public/90-278-1.PB.pdf>
- Bloom, M. et. al. (2007). Work and Marital Status in Relation to Depressive Symptoms and Social Support among Women with Coronary Artery Disease. *Journal of Women Health* 16(9):1305-1316.
- David, Ajibade (2016). The Influence of Socio-Demographic Factors on Job Stress Level in Foreign-Owned Manufacturing Companies in Ogun State, Nigeria. Nigeria: Lokoja-Ankpa Road.
- De Nobile, J.J. and McCormick, J. (2011). Occupational Stress of Catholic Primary School Staff: A Study of Biographical Differences, *International Journal of educational Management*. 24 (6): pp. 492-506.
- CNN Philippines (2017). Retrieved from: <http://cnnphilippines.com/lifestyle/2015/09/23/Filipinos-top-causes-of-stress-job-traffic-money.html>
- European Company Survey (2013). Retrieved from: <https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/surveys/european-surveys/european-company-survey-2013>
- International Labour Organization ILO (2016). Workplace Stress: A Collective Challenge. Retrieved from: https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/@ed_protect/@protrav/@safework/uments/publication/wcms_473267.pdf
- Jahan, H., and Sharma S. (2017). Occupational Stress in Upper Primary School. *AISECT University, Raisen*. Vol. 3 Issu J.
- Johnson, J. (2018, September 5). How to Tell if Stress is Affecting your Sleep. *Medical News Today*. Retrieved from: <https://www.medicalnewstoday.com/articles/322994.php>.
- Kaur, S. (2011). Comparative Study of Occupational Stress among Teachers of Private and Government Schools in Relation to their Age, Gender and Teaching Experience *International Journal of Experience. International Journal of Educational Planning and Administration* 1(2) 151-160.
- Klassen, R.M., (2010). Effects of Teachers' Self-Efficacy and Job Satisfaction: Teacher Sex, Years of Experience and Job Stress. *Journal of Educational Psychology*. 102 (3):pp741-756.
- Mai, Ngoc Khuong and Vu, Hai Yen, (2016). Investigate the Effects of Job Stress on Employee Job Performance: A Case Study at Dong Xuyen Industrial Zone, Vietnam. *International Journal of Trade, Economics and Finance* vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 31- 37, 2016.

- MaxLiving Health Expert (2018). What is Emotional Stress can Affect your Spine + Overall Health. Retrieved from: <https://maxliving.com/healthy-articles/emotional-stressandhow>.
- Mayo Clinic Health Expert (2017). Relaxation Techniques: Try These Steps to Reduce Stress. Retrieved from: <https://www.mayoclinic.org/healthy-lifestyle/stress-management/in-depth/relaxation-technique/art-zoo45368>.
- Mmaduakonam, A.E and Orizu, N. (2014). Socio-Demographic Predictors of Occupational Stress Among Secondary School Teachers in Anambra State, Nigeria, Counselling Implications. The European Conference on Psychology and the Behavioral Sciences
- Mondal, J., Shrestha, S., & Bhaila, A. (2011). School Teachers: Job Stress and Job Satisfaction, Kaski, Nepal. International Journal of Occupational Safety and Health, Vol. 1 No. 27-3. Retrieved from: <http://eujournal.org./files/journals/1/articles//90-278-1-PB.pdf>
- National Heart, Lung and Blood Institute (2015). Healthy Eating Plan. Retrieved from: <https://www.nhlbi.nih.gov/health/education/lose-wt/eat/calories.htm>
- Philippine News Agency (2018). DepEd Raises Concern over Leyte Teacher's Suicide. Retrieved from: <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1041810>
- Popoola, BI and Ilugbo, E.A., (2010). Personality Traits as Predictors of Stress among Female Teachers in Osun State Teaching Service. Edo Journal of Counseling 3(2):173-188.
- Scott, E., (2019). How to Reduce Stress with Breathing Exercises. Retrieved from: <https://www.verywellmind.com/how-to-reduce-stress-with-breathing-exercise-3144508>.
- Sissons, B. (2018, December 17). What Causes a Loss of Appetite? Medical News Today. MediLexicon, Int., 17 Dec. 2018.web.8 Jun. 2019. Retrieved from: <https://www.medicalnewstoday.com/articles/324011.php>.
- Turna, H. (2014). Stress Resources and Coping Methods with Stress for Teachers (The example of Edirne province/Keşan. Master Thesis, Okan University, İstanbul. Retrieved from: <http://tez2.yok.gov.tr/>.
- Vespi, L. (2019). Top Ten Personal Habits. Stone Circle Coaching. Retrieved from: <https://.stonecirclecoaching.com/ho-to-article/top-ten-personal-habits/>